

Opening new horizons with the first human brain in vivo experiments at 11.7T

F. Mauconduit¹, V. Gras¹, A. Amadon¹, A. Massire², C. LeSter¹, D. Le Bihan¹, M. Luong³, M. Bottlaender⁴, A. Vignaud¹, N. Boulant¹

¹University Paris-Saclay, CEA, CNRS, BAOBAB, NeuroSpin, Gif sur Yvette, France

²Siemens Healthcare SAS, Courbevoie, France

³IRFU, CEA, Gif sur Yvette, France

⁴University Paris-Saclay, CEA, Uniact, NeuroSpin, Gif sur Yvette, France

Synopsis (100 words 4 sections)

Motivation: Ultra-high magnetic field MRI offers new opportunities due to its higher SNR and CNR.

Goals: After receiving the authorization for scanning 20 adult healthy volunteers on the whole-body Iseult MRI scanner, we performed a preliminary MRI investigation to acquire the first brain images at 11.7T.

Approach: Using a homemade multi-transmit multi-receive head coil and parallel transmission, 3D anatomical images were acquired with multiple sequences and tissue contrasts at high resolution.

Results: In this study, high quality whole brain images acquired at 11.7T on the Iseult MRI scanner are presented for the first time to the MR community.

Impact (40 words max): Showing for the first time in vivo brain images acquired at 11.7T on the whole-body Iseult MRI scanner, this study reveals first potential and challenges of such systems to the ultra-high field MR community.

Primary category and subcategory:
Physics & Engineering / High-Field MRI

Secondary category and subcategory:

Main body (750 words max)

Introduction: Pushing the boundaries of field strength in MRI, this study reports the first in vivo human brain images acquired at 11.7T on the whole-body Iseult MRI scanner¹. Approval to scan in vivo 20 adult healthy volunteers (18-40 years old) at 11.7T was obtained from the French National Regulatory Body (ANSM) and the local ethics committee in Feb 2023. This first protocol consisted mostly of evaluating the safety for subjects exposed to the main magnetic field, for which results will be communicated elsewhere, and perform preliminary MRI testing and investigations with 1h30 long exams.

Methods: Informed consent was obtained from all volunteers. The 90-minute exam included the following sequences: localizer, B_0 mapping and shimming, B_0 and B_1^+ mapping for parallel transmission (pTx) pulse design, 3D multi-echo GRE in pseudo-CP mode (phase-shimming) and pTx, 3D slab-selective T_2^* -weighted GRE, 3D T_1 -weighted MP2RAGE and 3D T_2 -weighted SPACE. The Iseult 11.7T whole-body scanner has been equipped with the SC72 whole-body gradient coil (Siemens Healthcare, Erlangen, Germany). Experiments were also carried out with a homemade pTx RF coil whose design is described in². SAR was explicitly taken into account in the RF pulse design using first level mode with virtual observation points derived from homemade electromagnetic simulations and using the RF safety management strategy described in³. RF pulses were designed with k_T -points⁴, k_T -spokes⁵ and GRAPE⁶ depending on the sequences. The complex RF coefficients were optimized simultaneously with the transmit k-space trajectory⁷.

Results: Figure 1 shows B_0 maps of one subject after a 2nd-order B_0 shimming procedure. The resulting inhomogeneity (standard deviation over the 3D brain) was evaluated around 90Hz. Figure 1 also depicts individual B_1^+ maps of the transmit coil. In the default pseudo CP-mode, the peak total power necessary to achieve 180° flip angle in 1 ms was found to be 5.2 kW, on average over the 3 dimensional brains and over the subjects. Figure 2 compares a sagittal 3D-GRE multi-echo using the pseudo-CP mode versus a tailored dynamic pTx solution with a 830 μ s-long 7-kT points pulse, showing great mitigation of the RF field inhomogeneity problem with dynamic-pTx. Figure 3 highlights the exquisite contrast obtained with a high in-plane resolution T_2^* -weighted 3D slab-selective GRE with pTx (TE=15 ms, 0.22×0.22×1.2 mm³). High-resolution (0.55 mm isotropic) T_1 and T_2 -weighted 3D anatomical images with pTx are finally provided in Fig.4 and Fig.5, showing again mitigation of the RF field inhomogeneity problem and high SNR despite the high resolutions.

Discussion: The increase in B_0 inhomogeneity is consistent with a linear trend versus field, reflecting Iseult meeting its field homogeneity specifications. Due to time-constraints, comparisons of pseudo-CP versus pTx could not be systematically conducted for all sequences. The results reported in Fig.2 however highlight the mitigation of the B_1^+ field inhomogeneity problem we could achieve at 11.7T, which was further confirmed with other sequences, e.g., including refocusing pTx pulses (Fig.5). Due to the current architecture of the transmit RF coil and the increased power losses at 500 MHz, yet it has been difficult so far to achieve complete magnetization inversion everywhere in the brain. More work therefore is under way to tackle this problem with different transmit channels pairing² or different RF coil designs⁸, which we expect by the same token will increase SNR. Our results also

emphasize the need to further accelerate sequences and develop robust motion correction methods to achieve ultra-high resolutions when motion-induced field fluctuations are accentuated. These topics are currently the subject of current research to unleash the full potential of 11.7T MRI.

Conclusion: This work reports the first brain images acquired at 11.7T on adult healthy volunteers. The results remain preliminary given the limited number of subjects scanned so far and the apparent need of always refining protocols and methods for more optimal acquisitions. Given the severity of the RF field inhomogeneity, parallel transmission hereby appears unavoidable. The images however reveal already superb tissue contrast and pave the way for exciting and unique exploration of the human brain at unprecedented field strength.

References:

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Figure 1. B_0 and B_1^+ maps in the brain of volunteer #8 in transverse, coronal, and sagittal orientations. B_0 maps are expressed in Hz and were measured using a 3-echo non-selective 3D-GRE acquired in sagittal (2.5mm isotropic, total acquisition time of 60s). B_1^+ maps were measured using an interferometric magnetization-prepared 2D turbo-FLASH at a resolution of 5mm isotropic in 4min. Individual B_1^+ transmit channels are depicted in amplitude and phase, expressed in μT per volt and radians respectively.

Figure 2. Sagittal views of T_2^* -weighted isotropic 0.8 mm whole brain pseudo-CP (top row) vs k_T -points (bottom row) at different echo times (from left to right, TE = 3.2, 7.2, 11.2 and 15.6 ms) on volunteer #2. Acquisition parameters were 3D non-selective sagittal orientation, TR=25ms, Flip Angle=10°, CAIPIRINHA acceleration 2x2 and a scan time of 6min14.

Figure 3. T_2^* -weighted 3D slab-selective using a 3-spoke pTx pulse with high in-plane resolution ($0.22 \times 0.22 \times 1.2 \text{ mm}^3$) in axial views (top row) on volunteer #6. Coronal and sagittal views (bottom row) show the slab coverage over the brain. Acquisition parameters were TE=15ms, TR=29ms, a receive bandwidth of 168Hz/pixel, GRAPPA 4 in R>>L phase encode direction and a scan time of 11min31.

Figure 4. Sagittal, coronal and axial UNI images of a 3D T_1 -weighted MP2RAGE acquisition at 0.55mm isotropic resolution on volunteer #9. Acquisition parameters were 3D non-selective sagittal orientation, $TR=5200ms$, $T_{11}=1130ms$, $T_{12}=3730ms$, flip angles of 4° and 2° in consecutive GRE trains, GRAPPA 4 in A>>P phase encode direction and a scan time of 10min08. Spin inversion and excitation were realized using universal (simultaneous design across 5 B_0 , B_1^+ maps) GRAPE pulses of duration 10 ms and 0.3 ms respectively.

Figure 5. Sagittal, coronal and axial views of a 3D T_2 -weighted SPACE acquisition at 0.55mm isotropic resolution on volunteer #8. Acquisition parameters were 3D non-selective sagittal orientation, $TR=6s$, GRAPPA 3x2 in phase and partition directions respectively and a scan time of 13min20. Excitation and refocusing were realized using a single symmetric scalable GRAPE universal pulse of duration 1.4 ms designed across 5 B_0 , B_1^+ maps.